

A New Synthesis of Dicinnamoylmethane.

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The similarity of the vinyl group to phenyl in some of its reactions and in the properties of the corresponding derivatives was noticed by Norris and Couch (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **42**, 2329), who prepared vinyl phenyl ketone by the condensation of benzoyl chloride with ethylene in presence of aluminium chloride. A similar synthesis of benzylidene acetone was achieved a little earlier (Langlois, *Comp. rend.*, 1919, **168**, 1052), the reactants being styrene and acetyl chloride and the condensing agent stannic chloride. Such a method offers an attractive synthesis of dicinnamoylmethane (I, R, R' = H) and its derivatives, such as curcumin (I, R = OH, R' = OMe). The process has actually been found feasible, the interaction of malonyl chloride with two molecules of styrene and stannic chloride yielding a small amount of dicinnamoylmethane. The desired substance was isolated from much resinous matter by means of its copper derivative. Dicinnamoylmethane and curcumin have both been previously synthesised (Lampe and Milobedzka, *Ber.*, 1918, **46**, 2235; Lampe, *Ber.*, 1918, **51**, 1347) employing acetosacetic ester.

(I)

Malonyl chloride and bromide have been little exploited for synthetical purposes. Fleicher, Hittel and Wolf (*Ber.*, 1920, **53**, 1847) have observed that malonyl bromide gave better results than the chloride in the preparation of indandiones by its action on acenaphthene. They prepared the bromide for the first time by passing hydrogen bromide through malonyl chloride and fractionating the product. In the present work malonyl bromide has been made by treating the acid with thionyl bromide (Mayes and Partington, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **129**, 2594). The reaction was tried under widely varying conditions, with and without solvents. In every case considerable decomposition of the thionyl bromide was noticed, followed by separation of pure sulphur as long well-defined needles.

The best yield was obtained by treatment of carefully dried malonic acid with a large excess of thionyl bromide at 100 mm. pressure on the water-bath during two hours and fractionation of the mixture in *vacuo*.

It was found that the replacement of malonyl chloride by bromide in the preparation of dicinnamoylmethane affected the yield but little.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Dicinnamoylmethane.—The reaction was carried out in a three-necked flask fitted with a mechanical stirrer, a separating funnel and a condenser carrying a calcium chloride tube. To a solution of styrene ([“Organic Syntheses,” VIII, p. 84], 6 g.) and malonyl chloride ([McMaster and Ahman, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 146], 4 g.) in dry redistilled carbon disulphide (20 g.) cooled in ice, a solution of freshly distilled stannic chloride (14 g.) in carbon disulphide (14 g.) was added drop by drop during one hour. Stirring was continued at room temperature for three hours. A dark-red oil had then separated. Crushed ice and dilute hydrochloric acid were then introduced and the whole vigorously shaken. The mixture was extracted with ether, the ether extract washed with water until neutral and the ether removed. On steam-distilling the residue in order to remove any unchanged styrene and cooling, the oily mass solidified and was collected and dried. The powdered material was then refluxed with diethylaniline for an hour, cooled, treated with excess of dilute hydrochloric acid and the whole extracted with ether. The extract was washed with water and mechanically shaken with saturated aqueous copper acetate solution for a few hours. The bulky bluish-green precipitate which had separated was collected, decomposed with dilute sulphuric acid and the diketone taken up with ether. The product obtained from the washed and dried ether extract was apparently a mixture, but on extraction in a Soxhlet with low-boiling petroleum ether led to a homogeneous, crystalline substance, which was collected and recrystallised from dilute alcohol. The dark yellow needles (0.27 g.), m. p. 144°, corresponded in every particular (fluorescence with concentrated sulphuric acid, precipitate with copper acetate solution, colouration with ferric chloride and dye-trial on unmordanted wool) with the dicinnamoylmethane of Lampe and Milobedzka (*loc. cit.*). (Found: C, 82.8; H, 5.9. Calc. C, 82.6; H, 5.8 per cent.)

Malonyl bromide.—When malonic acid was treated with thionyl bromide at atmospheric pressure on the water-bath, it was found that little malonic acid went into solution, while the thionyl bromide decomposed rapidly with evolution of sulphur dioxide, hydrogen bromide and bromine. Various solvents were then tried, but fractionation of the product led to poor yields of malonyl dibromide. In several experiments, a bright orange liquid (which solidified partly on standing) was obtained at 110-120°/10 mm; its bromine value corresponded to that of malonyl monobromide (Found: Br, 34.9. $C_3H_3O_3Br$ requires Br, 34.8 per cent.): no reference to this substance is found in the literature. One typical experiment using ether as solvent may be described. Malonic acid (10 g.), thionyl bromide (60 g.) and dry ether (50 c.c.) were mixed; there was a vigorous reaction and after two hours separation into two layers was noticed—a pale-yellow fluorescent layer and a deep-red lower layer. In addition there were long stout needles, which were collected and identified as sulphur. A little of the top layer was pipetted out and the bromine estimated. (Found: Br, 39.3. $C_3H_3O_3Br$ requires Br, 34.8. $C_3H_3O_2Br_2$ requires Br, 69.6 per cent.) More thionyl bromide (5 c.c.) was added; vigorous reaction again took place and a clear homogeneous solution was obtained. After warming on the water-bath for two hours under reflux, the ether was removed and the residue fractionated at 9 mm. pressure. The following fractions were collected and the bromine value of each was determined.

Boiling point.	Percentage of bromine.
40-50°	50.5
50-55°	69.2
55-60°	25.2
5-95°	31.5
95-105°	34.5

Of the fraction 50-55°, which was obviously the required dibromide, only 3.5 g. were obtained. A quantitative test for sulphur showed that no appreciable amount was present.

The process finally adopted was to treat carefully dried malonic acid with eight times the weight of thionyl bromide on the water-bath under a reflux, the pressure being maintained at 100 mm. so that the thionyl bromide was kept gently boiling. At the end of two hours, the mixture was distilled in *vacuo*, the fraction 50-55°/9 mm. being collected; yield 30-40 per cent. (Found: Br, 69.8.

$C_3H_2O_2Br_2$ requires Br, 69.6 per cent.) The lower fractions consisting mainly of thionyl bromide were preserved and by redistillation at 100 mm. pressure, a certain amount of thionyl bromide was recovered. The action of thionyl bromide on other organic acids is being studied.

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